

New PV encapsulants: assessment of change in optical and thermal properties and chemical degradation after UV aging

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ABSTRACT

This work aims to investigate the change in chemical and physical properties of different polymeric materials, potentially usable for photovoltaic modules encapsulation, caused by UV aging. Three classes of polymeric materials have been examined: ethylene-vinyl-acetate (EVA), thermoplastic polyolefins (TPO) and polyolefin elastomers (POE). EVA is currently the most used encapsulant in the photovoltaic field; TPO and POE are new materials, alternative to EVA, which can allow to overcome some of the reliability problems of photovoltaic modules linked to the degradation of EVA properties. Of each of these three material classes, different commercially available encapsulating polymer films, with different chemical formulations, have been examined. Stressful environmental conditions have been simulated in a climatic chamber and the associated changes in optical, thermal and chemical properties of the different encapsulants have been analysed and compared before and after UV aging. The link between the chemical structure, formulation and degradation of the encapsulants with their lifetime under simulated conditions of UV stress has been investigated by the assessment of the changes in thermal stability, optical transmittance, crystallinity, yellowness index and chemical degradation. This study helps to better understand the causes of the module performance reduction due to the degradation of the encapsulant material and is a guide for the selection of encapsulant films with improved characteristics, for the manufacture of more durable PV modules.

1. Introduction

In the manufacturing of photovoltaic (PV) modules, the most often used encapsulant to protect c-Si cells from environmental stress factors is EVA, due to its low cost, good optical and mechanical properties and long-term field experience [1]. In the module lamination process, EVA polymeric film is cross-linked and transformed from the original thermoplastic and opaque material into an elastomeric, highly transparent material. During PV module lifetime, EVA undergoes different stresses due to temperature, oxygen, humidity, UV irradiation, resulting in thermo- and photo-degradation phenomena, which leads to the deterioration of its mechanical, optical and thermal properties. The degradation reactions lead to the formation of different by-products such as lactones, ketones, acetaldehyde and acetic acid [2]. Acetic acid release is particularly harmful because promotes the metallization corrosion, encapsulant delamination, discoloration, potential induced degradation (PID) and polymer autocatalytic degradation, resulting in a loss of PV module efficiency [3,4]. In order to overcome the PV modules reliability issues related to degradation of EVA properties, alternative encapsulants

such as polyolefin elastomer (POE)-based and thermoplastic polyolefin (TPO)-based materials are starting to get attention. POE and TPO are both polyethylene-based encapsulants. TPO does not crosslink chemically, but it has small crystalline segments or ionic clusters in its morphology, that act as physical cross-links below the melting point. It does not contain Vinyl Acetate (VAc) segments, so does not release acetic acid, minimizing the occurrence of corrosion and delamination. It is fabricated without a peroxide curing agent, has few chemical interactions and requires a short lamination time (about 10 min), reducing the production costs [5]. Instead, POE, like EVA, by curing agents, chemically cross-links, but being also free of VAc segments, does not produce acetic acid and therefore there is no occurrence of related failure modes. Moreover, other advantages linked to the use of these polymers are represented by the fact that TPO and POE have a higher volume resistivity compared to EVA, and are less permeable to moisture and sodium, so mitigate PID effect [6,7]

However, all the encapsulant films used in the study are sensitive to thermo- and photo-oxidation, which lead to the chain scission and structural changes [8,9]. Hence, to improve the resistance to

degradation due to UV light, the encapsulants need adequate stabilization, but since the base polymers show different stability against UV light, different degrees/types of stabilization are necessary for each encapsulant.

Generally, the encapsulants produced for PV modules are not pure polymers. During their formulation are added some additives: curing agents, adhesion promoters, UV absorbers, antioxidants, UV stabilizers, which affect their performance and are susceptible to degradation. EVA discoloration, for example, can be also caused by the interaction and/or decomposition of some additives, leading to the formation of chromophores [10].

Nowadays, although POE- and TPO-based encapsulants are commonly marketed, they are relatively new in solar applications, then the field data are limited and few long-term durability studies are available in literature. The few studies focused on aging of POEs and TPOs have shown that these encapsulants are subjected to UV aging, susceptible to photooxidation of the polymer chain and depletion of additives and stabilizers [11–13]. The optical degradation after exposure to UV radiation is manifested by the changes in optical transmittance and yellowness index. It has been observed that initially, transmittance of a TPO-based encapsulant increases and then gradually decreases, suggesting a degradation related to a reduction in crystallinity later compensated by chemical discoloration [14]. Some studies on Damp Heat (DH) test and UV aging have noted that UV stress carried out on TPOs and POEs, is much stricter than DH and causes depletion of stabilizers and subsequent polymers degradation [15]. The depletion of the UV absorbing additive has been highlighted by an increase in transmittance exhibited from some encapsulants.

However, the durability and reliability of PV modules manufactured with TPO and POE and subjected to accelerated UV aging, have been poorly studied in previous scientific works. In particular, a link lacks between the UV ageing and prediction of the materials degradation phenomena. In this work, the optical and chemical properties and thermal behaviour of 11 different polymer films belonging to three classes of encapsulants have been investigated and compared before and after UV aging. The screening of the specific characteristics and the comparative investigation of their variations following accelerated UV aging, for such a large number of materials, constitute a novelty in the literature. In particular, this research highlights the correlation between the variations in optical transmittance, crystallinity, thermal stability, yellowing, chemical degradation of polymeric films, with exposure to UV radiation, in climatic conditions simulating those in the field, during the operation of a module. The changes in their optical performance and in crystallinity, and the thermal and chemical degradation have been investigated by thermogravimetric analysis (TGA), differential scanning calorimetry (DSC), Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR), colorimetry and UV-Vis spectroscopy. Finally, the results of the characterizations before and after UV ageing allow to determine the correlation between optical performance and changes in crystallinity, as well as the link between reliability and durability of a PV encapsulant and its polymer structure or additive formulation. Since the different encapsulants tested in this study are of commercially available quality and come from different suppliers, it is likely that they contain different stabilization packages which are not disclosed by the manufacturers. Therefore, it is not possible to compare the stability of the base polymer against UV and stabilization packages. This study aims to carry out an extensive comparative analysis of different fully formulated and functional encapsulating films with respect to their durability and stability against UV aging and is useful for further research in the formulation field of new low cost PV encapsulants, to improve the performance, durability and oxidation resistance.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Encapsulant Jims

Uncured commercial encapsulants have been purchased by companies that produce them for the photovoltaic sector and provided in sheet form. In detail, EVA-05, EVA-05HTL, POE-05 and POE-05HTL were provided by SATINAL; EVA-3M and TPO-3M by LUX s.r.l. — SOLBIAN; POE-8110 and POE-8510 by 3M; TPO and TPO-m by MG LAV Plastiche; EVA-MW by MR WATT — Vistasolar. Fresh film rolls have been used for the tests. In [Table 1](#), the specific features of the polymers used in this work, provided by the manufacturers, are listed. All samples are light in color, only EVA-MW is completely transparent.

In order to investigate the UV ageing impact on the properties, characteristics and structure of the different classes of encapsulant polymers, five kinds of characterisations have been carried out. Thermal stability, crystallinity, optical transmittance, yellowing and chemical degradation of the materials have been investigated as a function of UV dose and aging time. The procedures indicated in the standard IEC 62788 were followed for the materials characterizations. [Fig. 1](#) shows a schematic diagram of the experimental approach and the methodology used in the research.

2.2. Thermal analysis

Thermogravimetric Analysis (TGA) and Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC) have been carried out using a Simultaneous Thermal Analyzer (STA) 6000 - Perkin Elmer. Samples have been cut into circular disc shapes weighing approximately 10 mg and placed in a crucible made of alumina. TGA has been carried out with a heating rate of 20°C/min from 150 to 700°C, under nitrogen flow of 20 mL/min. For DSC measurements, each sample has been subjected to a first heating run from 20 to 200°C, followed by a cooling run from 200 to 20°C and a second heating run from 20 to 200°C, for the investigation of melting and crystallization processes. Heating rate has been set to 15°C/min and thermograms were recorded under nitrogen flow of 20 mL/min. The reported results are the average of three independent measurements on the samples.

2.3. UV-Vis analysis

The optical properties of all encapsulants have been measured using a Lambda 1050+ UV-Vis/NIR spectrometer (PerkinElmer). Spectra were recorded from 250 to 1250 nm a resolution of 1 nm and 8 scans, with an integrating sphere from 150 mm InGaAs. The samples were measured in transmittance mode.

2.4. Colorimetric analysis

Yellowness index (YI) measurement has been carried out by a portable colorimeter (PCE Instruments, model: PCM-CSM 5), at 10° observer angle, 8°/d sphere geometry and a D65 light source. The white and black calibration has been made before the YI measurement and each sample has been measured in triplicate.

2.5. ATR-FTIR analysis

ATR-FTIR spectroscopy has been used to study the chemical changes that occur in the materials as a result of the UV aging. FTIR—ATR spectra were collected on a Spectrum Two - Perkin Elmer spectrometer equipped with an ATR (attenuated total reflectance) detector using a diamond cell, in the wavelength range of 4000–400 cm⁻¹, at a spectral resolution of 4 cm⁻¹ over 32 scans. A background of the diamond cell was performed for each analysis. Spectra have been recorded by contacting the ATR crystal directly onto the surfaces of each sample and have been collected before and after each UV irradiation. All displayed spectra

Table 1
Commercial name and specifics of used encapsulants.

Sample	Cross-linking degree (%)	Thickness (µm)	Density (gZ cm ³)	Lamination Conditions	Optical Transmittance (%)	UV-cut off Wavelength (nm)	Melting Temperature (°C)	Refractive Index
EVA-MW	n.a.	460	n.a.	Ultra-fast	> 90	360	n.a.	n.a.
EVA-OS	> 85	450-500	n.a.	10min, 145-150°C	91	360	65-70	1.48
EVA-05HTL	85	450-500	n.a.	10min, 145-150°C	91	300	65-70	1.48
EVA-3M	n.a.	400-550	0.92	3-13 min, 145-155°C	91	390	n.a.	1.49
POE-05	> 70	450-500	0.87	15 min, 150-160°C	91	360	65-75	1.48
POE-OSHTL	> 70	450-500	0.87	15 min, 150-160°C	91	300	65-75	1.48
POE-8110	n.a.	450-800	0.88	4-11min, 160°C	91	310	n.a.	1.49
POE-8510	n.a.	450-800	0.88	4-11 min, 160°C	91	350	n.a.	1.49
7PO	/	200-600	0.95	8-15 min, 140-160°C	> 91	n.a.	> 90	1.48
TPO-m	/	100-800	0.95	3-6 min, 130-160°C	> 91	n.a.	> 90	1.48
TPO-3M	/	200-800	0.90	n.a.	> 85	n.a.	n.a.	1.48

n.a. = not available.

Fig. 1. Synthetic diagram of experimental research methodology.

have been normalized with respect to the intensity of the peak at 2850 cm⁻¹, which is referred to methylene groups of polyethylene chain.

2.6. UV accelerated aging test

The purpose of the test is to accelerate the photodegradation processes occurring in the encapsulant material for evaluating its UV stability, on which the PV module reliability depends. The aging test has been carried out in thermal chamber type UV 3000 from Angelantoni Industries Spa (Italy), equipped with metal halide arc lamps to simulate the sunlight, under condition of 60 % relative humidity and 60°C temperature. Lamp spectrum measurements were carried out using a spectroradiometer type SR, 9910 V7 from Macam Photometrics Ltd (Scotland). The lamp intensity was recorded as a function of wavelength in the range 240-640 nm with a step wavelength of 1 nm and the scan time of 100 ms per step. The samples were exposed to irradiation intensity of 22, 74, 126 and 214 kWh/m², during four consecutive steps.

3. Results and discussions

3.1. Thermal characterization of unaged encapsulants

All the commercial encapsulant films considered in this work have been analysed by TGA to study their thermal stability and thermal decomposition stages. EVA shows two-stage degradation, the first one is due to the deacetylation and starts around 260°C, the second one is due to the polyethylene main chain decomposition [17]. Unlike EVA, POE and TPO have a single stage of degradation, at ca. 370°C and 340°C respectively, which is due to main polymer chain scission [18]. Fig. 2 shows TGA curves of three representative samples of each of the three encapsulants classes tested: EVA-MW, POE-05 and TPO-3M.

The onset temperatures (Tonset) of the transition stages, given by the intersection of the extrapolated baseline and the tangent to the point of maximum slope, have been calculated and listed in Table 2 for all encapsulants.

EVA is thermally stable up to 300°C. In a PV module due to cell defects, hot spots are created and the local temperature reaches up to ca. 300°C [19a]. At this temperature, EVAs undergo deacetylation, while POEs and TPOs provide better performance without decomposition up to 400°C [20]. POEs are the most thermally stable encapsulants.

Fig. 2. TGA curves of EVA-MW, POE-05 and TPO-3M encapsulant films.

Table 2

Table 2. T_{onset} of all encapsulants, calculated by TGA analysis before UV aging.

Encapsulant	T_{onset} (°C)	T_{onset} (°C)
	First stage	Second stage
EVA-MW	256	408
EVA-05HTL	260	406
EVA-05	274	403
EVA-3M	274	412
POE-05	450	/
POE-05HTL	451	/
POE-8510	450	/
POE-8110	455	/
TPO	426	/
TPO-M	429	/
TPO-3M	421	/

3.2. Thermal stability of UV aged TPO, POE and EVA encapsulants

In the life time of a PV module manufactured with EVA, problems of corrosion of metal parts, PID effect, yellowing and delamination occur due to deacetylation. This increases when VA content increases in the copolymer. TGA results also provide a VA content estimation. In fact, the mass loss that occurs in the first stage of degradation, due to the acetic acid evolution by VA decomposition, allows to estimate the VA content. So, the VA content in each sample of EVA encapsulant has been estimated before and after aging, using Eq. (1).

$$E_{VA} = W_{VA} / W_{AA} * W_{FD} \text{ loss\%} \quad (1)$$

Where W_{VA} e W_{AA} are the molecular weights of vinyl acetate (VA) and acetic acid (AA), W_{FD} is the first stage decomposition weight loss. The optimum VA content should be 28 % to 33 % in EVA. Higher VA content accelerates the deacetylation and degradation of optical, mechanical, electrical properties in PV modules [21].

In Fig. 3, VA content is shown in the different EVA encapsulants, characterized before and after UV irradiation at doses of 0, 22, 74, 126

Fig. 3. VA % content in EVA encapsulants exposed at UV irradiance.

and 214 kWh/m². Due to aging induced by UV radiation, all EVA samples lose mass and show a similar tendency to lose VA.

TGA analysis allows to evaluate the variation of the T_{onset} of the various encapsulants caused by UV aging. In Fig. 4, changes in T_{onset} temperatures of the different encapsulants after exposition at increasing UV doses are shown. POE-05 and POE-05HTL are the most thermally stable encapsulants, in fact T_{onset} does not change as the UV dose increases. Instead, after UV aging, POE-8110 and POE 8510 undergo a T_{onset} decrease of 19.93 and 11.82°C respectively. TPO-m is thermally stable, T_{onset} of TPO-3M increases of 13.23°C and that of TPO-m decreases slightly.

In Fig. 4, it is also observed that T_{onset} of all EVA samples decreases with increasing UV aging. Between EVA samples, the thermally least stable one is EVA-3M, in fact its T_{onset} decreases of 16.92°C. However, among all studied encapsulants, even after UV aging, for POE samples, the polymer main chain degradation starts only around 438°C, providing better performances in field to PV modules manufactured with these polymers.

S.S. Thermal properties and crystallinity

Due UV aging, chemical processes such as the chain scission and physical processes such as the loss of an antioxidant/stabilizer additive or post crystallization phenomena, can lead to changes in thermal properties of the encapsulants [22]. Changes in the thermal properties have been studied by DSC analyses through a heat-cool-heat cycle. Irreversible chemical and reversible physical processes can be detected in the second and in the first heating curve of DSC measurement respectively, by changes in melting enthalpy and temperature [16]. Then, melting enthalpy changes have been used for evaluating the degree of crystallinity.

In the first heating, EVA shows two endothermic reaction peaks. The first peak, at lower temperature, is related to the melting of small irregular crystallite segments, while the second one, at higher temperature, is related to the actual melting point of large regular crystallite segments. In second heating, the first peak disappears, indicating a physical change in the crystal population of the material. Instead, the peak at higher temperature remains because chemical degradation does not occur [23].

In Fig. 5, DSC thermograms of three encapsulants, belonging to the three classes of polymers studied, are shown. DSC thermograms of the all samples are shown in Figs. S1—S3 of the supplementary material. In the first heating, the melting transition of the ethylene segment is associated with a peak with a shoulder, between 40°C to 80°C. In the second heating, it can be observed that the peaks have largely disappeared,

Fig. 4. T_{onset} of the second stage degradation for different EVA encapsulants and T_{onset} of thermal decomposition for different TPO and POE encapsulants before and after UV aging, calculated by TGA analysis.

Fig. 5. DSC thermograms for EVA-SM, TPO-m and POE-8510 encapsulants, before and after UV aging, under two heating steps.

suggesting that the previously formed structure has been eliminated and has not reformed during the cooling process. Moreover, for all classes of studied encapsulant, the second heating runs did not show any changes that could indicate chemical degradation processes during UV aging tests carried out in this work. Therefore, it can be concluded that the aging caused only reversible changes in all samples.

The peaks of the endothermic melting transition are rather broadened, probably because the smaller and less perfect crystals melt at temperatures below the thermodynamic melting point of the polymer and then recrystallize into larger, more perfect crystals. Since the aging tests have been carried out at a temperature between the polymer glass transition temperature and melting temperature, the result of this structural reorganization of the polymers, is a redistribution of melting points [22].

In the Table 3, the melting temperatures and crosslinking enthalpies of the studied encapsulants are listed. In the first heating, EVA-3M, EVA-MW, TPO, TPO-m and TPO-3M have higher melting temperatures. In the field operation, PV modules can reach temperatures higher than 90°C, so an encapsulant with a higher melting temperature and a broader melting range provides higher stability to PV module. In the second heating, a single endothermic peak remains. As effect of aging, for all EVA samples and for POE-05, this peak moves at higher temperatures. The increase in the melting temperatures for EVA indicates the occurrence of deacetylation reaction during UV aging. For POE-05HTL, POE-8510 and TPO, T_{jpp} remains constant, while for TPO-m and TPO-3M# Typ decreases slightly and for POE-8110, it decreases more significantly. EVAs and POEs crosslinking occurs in the range 135-180°C, so after the first heating, they are fully cross-linked. The enthalpy changes due to crosslinking of EVAs are higher than those of POEs. TPOs have no significant changes in T_{jpp} and $H_{crossli,Vi,g}$, confirming their thermoplastic nature.

In order to calculate the crystallinity degree of the encapsulants, the melting peak has been integrated and the melting enthalpy (AH_{typ})

Table 3

Melting temperatures of all encapsulants before and after UV aging and enthalpies obtained by DSC analysis. 1H and 2H are first and second heating respectively.

Unaged Sample		$T_{1,p}$ (°C) unaged	$T_{1,p}$ (°C) 4UV	$T_{2,p}$ (°C) unaged	$T_{2,p}$ (°C) 4UV	AH_{qpt} ; (J g ⁻¹) unaged
EVA-05	1H	46	46	74	71	14.54
	2H			71	82	
EVA-05 HTL	1H	46	50.1	73	74	12.52
	2H			68	81	
EVA-3M	1H	51	47	78	73	10.72
	2H			73	79	
EVA-MW	1H	58	46	78	73	13.38
	2H			75	79	
POE-05	1H	45	47	72	71	6.24
	2H			68	76	
POS 05HTL	1H	47	46	71	72	2.69
	2H			71	71	
POE-8510	1H	47	48	65	71	3.09
	2H			70	70	
POS 8110	1H	49	47	64	72	7.67
	2H			75	70	
TPO	1H	48	45	94	95	
	2H			94	94	
TPO-m	1H	56	47	89	93	
	2H			92	90	
TPO-3M	1H	56	47	106	104	
	2H			108	106	

calculated for both the curves of the first and second heating. The degree of crystallinity χ_c has been calculated according to Eq. (2):

$$\chi_c(\%) = \frac{(\Delta H_{mp})}{(\Delta H_0)} \cdot 100\% \quad (2)$$

where ΔH_{mp} is the specific enthalpy of melting of the sample and ΔH_0 is the specific enthalpy of melting for 100 % crystalline polyethylene. Since EVA, POE and TPO films are copolymers based on polyethylene, the ΔH_0 is 288 J/g [24].

In Fig. 6, the trend of crystallinity as a function of UV aging is shown for all encapsulants, after first and second heating. The fluctuating trend of the curves is an indication of the complex semi-crystalline nature of the polymers. Since the aging tests were carried out in a climatic chamber at 60°C, the aging temperature lies within the melting region. Therefore, during the tests, the smaller crystals can melt and crystallize again to form thicker crystals, which melt at higher temperatures.

As shown in Fig. 6, in the first heating, crystallinity of all EVA samples and all POE samples decreases initially, and then increases with the progress of UV aging, except for the POE-8510 for which it decreases slightly throughout the first heating. Instead, the crystallinity of TPO and TPO-3M increases during the first heating, while for TPO-m remains constant. TPO-3M has the highest crystallinity degree. The increase in the crystallinity of the encapsulants indicates the occurrence of secondary crystallization. Since heating and cooling rates, dwell temperature and duration affect the polymeric structure, the crystallinity changes are partially reversible.

In the second heating, there are no significant changes in crystallinity for almost all the samples, suggesting that polymers do not undergo chemical changes, but only physical aging effects. TPO samples are chemically more stable.

The different influence of ageing on the crystallinity of the encapsulants is likely related to various factors: the specific formulation, particularly the additives, initial crystallinity, melting temperature, and VA content in EVA samples [14]. Of the unaged samples, POE-8510 has the lowest degree of crystallinity (8 %), and the TPO-3M has the highest degree of crystallinity (24 %). The DSC curves of TPO samples show two peaks at melting temperatures (around 48°C and 97°C) higher than those of EVA and POE films. In fact, TPOs are cross-linked only physically and contain no side groups that could hinder crystallization of the PE sequences; hence, they exhibit a higher degree of crystallinity. Instead, due to cross-linking, EVAs and POEs have a less orderly structure. EVAs and POEs show a comparable melting behaviour and degree of crystallinity. However, POEs have a lower branches content than EVAs and hence less cross-linking.

Typically, a low degree of crystallinity is preferable as it generally provides greater optical transmittance, less stiffness, brittleness, and more flexibility/deformation in the PV modules. On the other hand, the

incidence of degradation mechanisms is greater on polymers with lower crystallinity. In fact, the migration of atmospheric oxygen or a degradation product generated during UV exposure is facilitated in structures with a lower degree of crystallinity. However, a certain crystallinity degree of the polymer is necessary to provide mechanical support to the module structure. In the first heating, after UV aging, all EVA samples show a decrease in crystallinity, little meaning only for EVA-MW; TPO and TPO-3M show a high increase in crystallinity, while TPO-m only a small drop; crystallinity of POE-05HTL increases, as well as that of POE-8110, while that of POE-8510 and POE-05 slightly decreases. The small variations in crystallinity recorded in the second heating are reported in Table 6.

4. Optical properties

The UV-Vis analysis allows to evaluate the transparency of the encapsulant films in the visible range, the presence of additives capable of absorbing the radiation in the UV range and the formation of unsaturated species, which are responsible for the discoloration in aged encapsulants. Additives such as peroxide-based curing agent, UV absorber and hindered amine light stabilizer are used to improve photo and thermo-oxidative stability of the encapsulants and then enhance their long-term performance [25]. During field exposure of a PV module, humidity, temperature cycling and UV radiation cause the polymer degradation. Among these factors, UV aging most intensely affects the polymers yellowing, thus decreasing their lifetime significantly. This leads to an increase in their yellowing, a decrease in their transmittance and a loss in PV module power over time. EVA photo-degradation begins from the VA units and increases with increasing the VA content. The optimum VA content should be between 18 and 33 % to have a right balance between transmittance, resistance against yellowing, thermal stability and mechanical stiffness and ductility [26]. In the formulation of the encapsulants for the photovoltaic industry, additives also are used to open the incident radiation window and allow the solar radiation to go through the polymer hitting most efficiently the cells. Some additives are able to increase around 1 % of yield of each cell [27]. However, the major polymers are sensitive to the UV part of the electromagnetic radiation. Lower is the wavelength of the UV light, higher is its harmful effect on the polymer chain. The challenge is to extend the life of the modules without polymer yellowing and its degradation, using a high yield encapsulant, resistant to the UV radiation harmful effects. By using the UV absorbent additives on the polymeric matrix, we can slow down its degradation process but we cannot completely avoid the problem.

The Fig. 7 presents the Transmittance % vs wavelengths of various unaged encapsulant films of EVA, TPO and POE, with different UV protection.

The UV absorbers provide UV absorption between 300 and 380 nm,

Fig. 6. Evolution of crystallinity over UV exposure of different encapsulants in the first and second heating (1H and 2H).

Fig. 7. UV-Vis transmission spectra of different unaged encapsulants.

the light stabilizers and antioxidants instead show strong absorption for $\lambda < 280$ nm. The curing agents decompose during the lamination, then doesn't show peaks in the UV spectrum. Anyway, the optical response (bandwidth and magnitude) of the additives is affected by their concentration and their interaction [28]. In Fig. 7, the peaks of the additives appear shifted to higher wavelengths. The peaks present at around 265 nm are associated to presence of antioxidants and light stabilizers, while those present at higher wavelengths (~ 310 nm), are UV absorbers.

Every sample has its specific absorbance cut-off wavelength at 10 % of transmittance. Below this wavelength the samples absorb the light. EVA-05HTL, POE-05HTL, POE-8110 and TPO are not UV stabilized while the other encapsulants are UV protected (UV stabilized samples with a cut off around 350 nm wavelength). In Table 4, $T_{10\%}$ at 550 nm and UV cut-off at 10 % T are listed for all unaged samples. In the visible region (400-800 nm), EVA-3M has the highest transmittance followed by EVA-MW, POE-05 and POE-05HTL. For unaged samples of EVA, the percentage transmittance is related to a high VA content that determines a decrease in the crystallinity [29]. EVA-3M has the highest UV cut-off wavelength at 366 nm, while due to the lack of UV absorbers, EVA-05HTL, POE-05HTL, POE-8110 and TPO are transparent in the UV region (250 - 400nm). POE-8510 is semi-transparent in the UV region (250—400 nm), which compensates the lower transmittance in the visible region and has three UV cut-off wavelengths due to the presence of additives.

Since the polymers are sensitive to the radiation that goes from 240 to 350 nm (all UV range), by using an encapsulant with cut off less than 350 nm we are challenging the life span of the module because the polymers are unprotected. This is a high risky, especially for panels that have to work in the areas of the world where the UV radiation is normally very intensive. In this case, the most suitable encapsulant will be the one that allows to get the right compromise between the 1 % gain in efficiency of the cells and the life shortage of the PV panel.

Table 4
%T at 550 nm and UV cut-off wavelength at 10 % T of unaged encapsulants.

Unaged encapsulant	% T at 550 nm (400 – 800 nm)	UV cut-off wavelength at 10 % T (nm)
EVA-MW	92	360
EVA-05HTL	90	N.D.
EVA-05	88	354
EVA-3M	94	366
POE-05	93	355
POE-05HTL	93	N.D.
POE-8510	85	255 - 278 - 373
POE-8110	90	N.D.
TPO	90	N.D.
TPO-m	90	364
MO-3M	87	362

N.D. = Not Detectable

The UV-Vis transmission spectra of the unaged encapsulants, in Fig. 7, show that in the UV region 250-400 nm, TPO, EVA-05HTL, POE-8110 and POE-05HTL, have $T_{10\%}$ values higher than other samples. That is, these encapsulants behave as high UV transparent compared to others. This behaviour is due to the reduced amount of UV stabilizing additives loaded in the formulation of these polymers. The stabilizers absorb and block the UV light. Instead, when an encapsulant film contains an UV absorber, the UV cut-off value of the film increases, thus allowing less light to reach the solar cell. However, since the UV part of the electromagnetic radiation is highly harmful for the polymers, the lower the wavelength of the UV light, the higher its damaging effect on the polymer chain. Hence reducing or avoiding appropriate UV stabilizers, certainly compromises the long-term durability of the encapsulant film [30,31]. The encapsulants with low UV cut-off, developed in the recently to gain around 1 % gain in the power output of the PV module, have a still uncertain long-time durability. The reduced use of UV absorbers in the formulation of encapsulants causes faster discoloration over time.

The most significant effects of UV aging for the polymers are discoloration, with subsequent loss of transmittance and then performance. In the case of EVA, UV aging also leads to VA loss in the form of acetic acid, which determines the PV module corrosion. In order to study the effects of UV aging, all samples have been exposed to four UV doses 22, 74, 126 and 214 kWh/m², indicated respectively with 1, 2, 3, 4 UV, in a climatic chamber. In Fig. 8, UV-Vis spectra of four EVA encapsulants exposed at four UV doses are shown.

Maximum transmittance values of EVA-05HTL progressively decrease over the exposure at four UV doses. After the fourth UV aging, its $T_{550\text{nm}}$ is 3.66. Likewise, a decrease in transmittance values in the blue range of the spectra (380 nm—500 nm) is observed and attributed to a chromophore formation and subsequent yellowing of the material. In fact, a light yellow-brown appearance has been observed at the central region of the EVA-05HTL sample. It has been observed that the type and amount of the antioxidant had a significant effect on the photo-stability of the EVA film and its discoloration can also occur due to reaction between curing agent and UV absorber during field exposure [32].

In Fig. 9, $T_{550\text{nm}}$ as a function of the UV dose is shown for EVA encapsulants.

A higher decrease in the transmittance value at 550 nm is observable for UV aged EVA-3M and EVA-MW. The changes of transmittance are 0.26 % for EVA-05, 3.66 % for EVA-05HTL, 6.62 % for EVA-3M and 5.46 % for EVA-MW. Upon UV aging, the percentage transmittance at 550 nm decreases in samples of higher VA content. In the region between 300 and 320 nm, a slight increase of the transmittance value, which might be correlated to the consumption of the UV absorbers is observed for EVA-05, while it is negligible for EVA-MW and EVA-3M. Then for these last two encapsulants the UV absorber degradation is

Fig. 8. UV-Vis spectra of four EVA encapsulants, before and after UV aging.

Fig. 9. Change in T % at 550 nm vs UV dose for different EVA encapsulants.

minimal.

In Fig. 10, the variation of the UV cut-off wavelength as a function of the UV dose is shown for all samples. With increasing UV dose, the cut-offs of TPO-3M, TPO-m and POE-8510 decrease more than the other encapsulants. EVA-05 and POE-05 have the lowest cut-off values but undergo a less variation upon exposure to UV radiation.

In Fig. 11, the UV-Vis spectra of different TPO encapsulants are shown. TPO does not have any UV absorber and its degradation, as a

Fig. 10. Change in UV cut-off wavelength at 10 % T vs UV dose for different encapsulants.

result of ageing process, is noticeable in the UV range where a strong decrease in transmittance is observed. The decrease in UV cut-off wavelength for TPO-m indicates the destruction of UV absorbing additives, caused by ageing. Instead, TPO-3M is more stable in the UV region.

In Fig. 12, the change in T % at 550 nm vs UV dose for the three TPO encapsulants is shown.

TPOs studied in this work have different chemical structures: TPO is

Fig. 11. UV-Vis spectra of three TPO encapsulants, before and after UV aging.

Fig. 12. Change in T % at 550 nm vs UV dose for different TPO encapsulants.

a copolymer ethylene/acrylate, TPO-m is a copolymer ethylene

acrylate/acrylamide, while TPO-3M is an oxidized low density polyethylene. The variations in the optical properties of these films are due not only to the presence or lack of UV absorber additives but also to the different basic chemical structure. Acrylate/acrylamide copolymers are used in photovoltaic devices because they have high electrical conductivity, on the other hand they are very sensitive to light and therefore undergo photodegradation [33a]. The trend in $\Delta T\%$ for TPO and TPO-m, observed in Fig. 12, indicates the deterioration of additives and the formation of degradation products as the UV dose increasing. However, at the end of the experiment, TPO-m shows greater degradation than TPO, probably due to its structure which contains acrylamide.

The increase in $\Delta T\%$ for TPO-3M may follow from the reduction in crystalline content of the materials [34]. TPO-3M is a semi-crystalline polymer with a smaller number of branches and a higher crystallinity than the other two TPOs. Semicrystalline polymers, below the glass transition temperature, have a structure made up of crystalline zones

Fig. 13. UV-Vis spectra of four POE encapsulants, before and after UV aging.

interspersed with glassy zones. During ageing, carried out in the temperature range between the glass transition temperature and the melting temperature, the glassy areas pass into the state of an undercooled liquid, therefore the structure becomes more amorphous. As seen in Fig. 6, initially, TPO-3M has the highest crystallinity degree among all TPOs but then it decreases with aging and consequently the film becomes more transparent, then AT % at 550 nm increases.

As a result of UV aging, POE-8110 exhibits a drop in transmittance in the UV region, probably associated with the formation of chromophores (Fig. 13). Compared to POE-05HTL, which also has high transmittance, POE-8110 is less resistant to degradation in the UV region and more resistant in the visible region. POE-05HTL suffered a high degradation already after the third UV aging and was completely degraded at the fourth UV aging.

In Fig. 14, the change in T % at 550 nm vs UV dose for the four POE encapsulants is shown.

A smaller loss of transmittance and a small decrease in wavelength cut-off, suggesting the good sealing of the UV absorber, have been observed for POE-05.

Moreover, for each sample, the YI change (YI) has been calculated as the difference between the value measured after each exposition to UV dose and value measured on the unaged sample.

Fig. 15 shows that the change in YI is increased as the UV dose increases for all the encapsulant types. POE-05HTL has shown a major increment in the change of YI value as compared to other materials, followed by EVA-05HTL and TPO-m.

5. Photo-degradation

ATR-FTIR allows to investigate the evolution of the chemical degradation and the formation of the byproducts as the material ages. UV aging causes structural changes in the polymers and as a result the functional groups in the molecules vary.

The infrared absorption peaks of the main functional groups in EVA, POE and TPO are listed in Table 5.

The FTIR spectra of unaged and UV aged EVA-MW and EVA-05HTL and other EVA encapsulants are given in the Fig. 16 and Fig. S4 of the supplementary material respectively. All EVAs spectra clearly show the characteristic bands of the copolymer of ethylene and vinylacetate and give indications about the presence of cross-linking agents in unaged films.

Crosslinking process of EVA is obtained via a radical reaction, using a peroxide compound or a peroxydicarboxylic acid as crosslinker [4]. All EVAs spectra show changes in the range 1170-1095 cm^{-1} and 780-750 cm^{-1} that are characteristic of a peroxide C—O—O group and five coupled of aromatic protons, respectively. In particular, the decrease of the bands at 1158 cm^{-1} and 766 cm^{-1} indicates the presence of an aromatic peroxy crosslinker (such as dicumyl peroxide) consuming during the UV aging. Before and after UV aging, changes are also observed in the ranges: 1705-1680 cm^{-1} corresponding to stretching N—C=O,

Fig. 14. Change in T % at 550 nm vs UV dose for different POE encapsulants.

1660-1640 cm^{-1} corresponding to alkene stretching C=C, and 1419-1400 cm^{-1} corresponding to bending =CH₂, which could be attributed to the curing agent triallyl isocyanurate.

In the spectra of EVA-05, EVA-05HTL and EVA-3M, the bands at 1700 cm^{-1} , 1648 cm^{-1} and 1410 cm^{-1} decrease, indicating the reaction of the allylic groups of the curing agent and their subsequent consuming during the aging process. In EVA-MW spectrum, a decrease of the band at 1558 cm^{-1} is also observed as a function of UV aging. It corresponds to aromatic stretching N=C which could be related to a co-curing agent such as the triallyl cyanurate [40].

To evaluate the aging of the encapsulants, the functional groups changes in the ranges 1800-1680 and 1180-1020 cm^{-1} have been considered, since the products of EVA photodegradation, which develop through the elimination of the ester, cause changes of the peak assigned to the ester carbonyl stretching at 1736 cm^{-1} and of the peak assigned to the ether stretching C—O—C at 1020 cm^{-1} . The species formed as a consequence of UV aging are carboxylic acids, ketones, aldehydes and lactones. The bands at 1175 cm^{-1} and 1715 cm^{-1} are characteristic of the vibrational modes of ketones derived from the photolysis reactions [10]. The shift of the peak at 1175 to 1160 cm^{-1} is characteristic of the stretching of the C—O—C group which appears when the branches of acetate are damaging and EVA chain is breaking [26]. As result of the branches breakage of the acetate groups, another band at 1780 cm^{-1} , characteristic of a new vibrational mode of carbonyl, appears and is associated with the formation of lactones. As a result of UV irradiation, the band around 1178 cm^{-1} , attributed to the C—O stretching of lactone, also appears increased. However, the amount of lactone formed as a result of aging, is less than that of ketone, since ketone formation is easier due to the conformational arrangements [41]. Moreover, in the FTIR spectra of EVAs, carbon double bonds can be seen in the peak appearing at 1641 cm^{-1} (C=C stretching), as a result of the chain damage and unsaturated species formation. Instead, peaks at 1540 cm^{-1} , at 861 cm^{-1} and at 809 cm^{-1} can be assigned to the triazine group of a amine light stabilizer, to the aromatic ring of phenol antioxidants and hydroxybenzophenones of a UV-absorber respectively [42].

For evaluating the encapsulants degradation, the region of the carbonyl (C=O) group has been analyzed and the peaks in the range 1800-1680 cm^{-1} have been integrated. In order to carry out a quantitative analysis, the peak area of the functional groups has been normalized with respect to the peak area of the methylene C—H symmetric stretching at 2850 cm^{-1} , since it is assumed that it does not change with respect to the other bands during ageing and is less likely to be overloaded compared to the one at 2921 cm^{-1} [43]. The Carbonyl Index (CI) has been calculated by Eq. (3):

$$\text{Carbonyl Index} = A_x/A_{2850} \quad (3)$$

where A₂₈₅₀ is the area of the C—H stretching vibration of the methylene and A_x is the area of the peak referred to C=O stretching vibration of each target functional group in the range 1780-1712 cm^{-1} . The areas of the overlapping peaks corresponding to C=O stretching vibrations at 1712 cm^{-1} (carboxylic acid), 1719 cm^{-1} (ketone), 1733 cm^{-1} (aldehyde), 1736 cm^{-1} (ester), and 1780 cm^{-1} (lactone) were calculated using OriginPro Software. In order to deconvolute the composite band profile in the 1800-1680 cm^{-1} carbonyl region, five parameters have been taken into account: the number of the component peaks, their positions, the peak shapes, the peak half-width and the form of the baseline. The location of the individual components of the carbonyl band has been initially performed on the basis of the literature studies. Then, detailed peak assignment has been obtained by derivative analysis of the experimental curves. The presence of negative and positive peaks, in the second and fourth derivatives respectively, suggested the contribute of seven components. The additional components pointed out by the derivative analysis have been important for the deconvolution best fitting of the overall band. The curve-fitting has been performed using Gaussian function. The overall goodness of the fit was assessed

Fig. 15. Change in YI for the encapsulant films after UV aging test. (a): EVAs; (b) POEs; (c) TPO.

Table S

Attribution of infrared absorption bands to functional groups of the encapsulant polymers (EVA, POE and TPO) [29,35–37]

Band characteristic	Functional group	Wavenumber (cm ⁻¹)
C-H bending	Methylene	721
C-H out-of-plane bending	Vinyl	910
C-H out-of-plane bending	R-CH=CH-R	950
=CH stretching	R-CH=CHt	995
C-O symmetric stretching	Acetate ester	1020
C-C stretching		1120
C-O-C stretching of ether	Ketone	1128
	Aliphatic ester	1150
	Lactone	1180
VA ester (C-O-C asymmetric stretching)		1236
Methyl of hydrocarbon (C-H bending)		1370
C-H scissoring	Methylene of hydrocarbon	1465
C=C stretching	Polyenes	1641
C=C vibration	Polyenes	1540
C=O stretching	Carboxylic acid	1712
	Ketone	1719
	Aldehydes	1733
	VA ester	1736
	Lactone	1780
C-H symmetric stretching of CHP	Methylene	2850
C-H asymmetric stretching of CHP	Methylene	2918
=CH stretching		3010
-OH stretching	Hydroxyl	3350-3465

according to the convergence of the fit given from the software. Fit analyses were chosen with convergence solutions with R² factor always better than 0.996. The absorption bands of esters and aldehydes are centred at 1736 cm⁻¹ and 1733 cm⁻¹, respectively and closely superimpose one another giving rise to a single band at about 1737 cm⁻¹, which cannot be resolved by deconvolution analysis. In Fig. 17, the CI for EVA samples, are shown. CI trend reveals that the high initial acid concentration is due to the loss of acetic acid that occurs during the first stage of EVA degradation. The artificial aging of EVAs causes no significant changes in the carbonyl index, only EVA-3M undergoes a more evident chemical degradation which may be due to oxidation in ethylene other than VA segment.

However, oxidation products containing carbonyl groups, such as ketons, aldehydes, carboxylic acids and lactones are formed in all EVAs. The calculation of the carbonyl index reveals that the ketones are the most predominant compound after aging. Their formation might occur during the acetaldehyde evolution process [26]. The increase in absorbance, attributed to ketonic C=O stretching at 1715 cm⁻¹, is greater than that of the other species, suggesting the preferential formation of ketones. EVA-3M is the most unstable of the four EVA samples, due to the presence of high levels of photoactive species which contribute to the photodegradation of the polymer. In the initial phase of aging, deacetylation involves a decrease in the concentration of the ester carbonyl group and therefore a decrease in the carbonyl index. At 3UV, however, an increase in absorption at 1737 cm⁻¹ is noted, probably due to the increase in the concentration of aldehydes. Unlike EVA, which has a polymer chain with polar functional groups (esters), TPOs and POEs have a polymer chain with non-polar functional groups (olefins). Therefore, a prominent carbonyl peak (C=O) around 1740 cm⁻¹ is

Fig. 16. ATR-FTIR spectra of unaged and UV aged EVA-MW and EVA-05HTL.

Fig. 17. Carbonyl index for EVA encapsulant films, referred to the variations of the C=O functional group.

absent in their spectra. Only POEs have a small peak around at 1700 cm⁻¹, of much smaller amplitude than the ester C=O vibration in EVAs, which may correspond to a residual peroxide curing agent [44]. In Figs. 18 and S5 in the supplementary material, FTIR spectra of POE

samples are shown. Upon UV aging, in the region 3600-3100 cm⁻¹, corresponding to the hydroxyl (-OH), in the region 1780-1650 cm⁻¹ and 1650-1620 cm⁻¹, corresponding to the carbonyl (C=O) and carbon double bond (C=C) respectively, new and broad bands have formed for

Fig. 18. ATR-FTIR spectra of unaged and UV aged POE-05HTL and POE-8110.

all encapsulants. In fact, the UV-induced polymers photooxidation takes place via formation of hydroperoxides, which decompose and produce ketones, aldehydes, esters, or carboxylic acids (C=O vibrations at 1780-1650 cm^{-1} and C-O-C vibrations at 1020-1180 cm^{-1}) [16a].

Moreover, after UV aging, the FTIR spectra of POE samples reveal certain changes also in the region 800-820 cm^{-1} , corresponding to the vibrations of an aromatic ring of hindered phenols (antioxidants) [42]. The appearance of new peaks at 875 and 908 cm^{-1} , related to =C-H vibrations, indicates degradation, probably also due to the consumption or decomposition of antioxidants and other additives.

In Fig. 19, CI of POE samples, calculated by integration of peaks areas corresponding to C=O vibrations in 1780-1680 cm^{-1} range are shown.

For all POEs, ketones are the most abundant oxidation products, followed by esters/aldehydes. POE-8110 and POE-8510 begin to age earlier than POE-05 and POE-05HTL, but after the fourth aging, they maintain greater chemical stability than POE-05HTL, which is the encapsulant that shows the greatest degradation between all POEs.

Also for TPO samples, the carbonyl region has been evaluated, which can be affected by oxidation of ethylene units. In Fig. 20, ATR-FTIR spectra of unaged and UV aged TPO and TPO-m encapsulants films are shown. TPO is a copolymer ethylene/acrylate, the peaks at 1736 cm^{-1} and 1160 cm^{-1} are characteristic of the C=O and C-O-C vibrations of acrylate. TPO-m is a copolymer ethylene acrylate/acrylamide, as can be seen from the peaks at 1638 cm^{-1} and 1556 cm^{-1} which are characteristic of the C=O and N-H vibrations of amide. Instead, TPO-3M is an oxidized low density polyethylene, its ATR-FTIR spectrum is shown

in Fig. S6 in the supplementary material.

For evaluating the chemical stability of TPOs, the peaks were integrated from 1800 to 1680 cm^{-1} and in Fig. 21, CI is shown.

Artificial aging of TPO and TPO-3M samples causes no significant changes in the carbonyl index; TPO-3M is the most chemically stable encapsulant. To compare the chemical stability of all encapsulants, the carbonyl index related to ketones has been reported in Fig. 22.

In EVAs, the evolution of acetic acid accelerates the discoloration and degradation, whereas in TPOs, not only the degradation happens to a lower extent, but also it starts at a later stage than EVA. The most chemically stable films are TPO-3M, EVA-MW and EVA-05, while EVA-3M undergoes the greatest degradation.

6. Conclusion

In this study, 11 encapsulating films used for PV modules fabrication, belonging to three different polymer classes: EVA, POE and TPO, were subjected to accelerated UV aging and the variation of their optical/thermal properties and chemical degradation were evaluated and compared. In Table 6, the results of the characterizations carried out are summarized and the variations of the specific characteristic properties of various encapsulants subjected to UV aging are highlighted.

Thermal properties analysis of the investigated polymeric films reveals that POE-05 and POE-05HTL are the most thermally stable encapsulants, followed by all TPOs. After UV aging, all POEs and TPO-3M show a small decrease in crystallinity, while TPO shows the

Fig. 19. Carbonyl Index for POE encapsulant films, referred to the vibrations of the C=O functional group.

Fig. 20. ATR-FTIR spectra of unaged and UV aged TPO and TPO-m encapsulant films.

Fig. 21. Carbonyl index for TPO encapsulant films, referred to the vibrations of the C=O functional group.

Fig. 22. Carbonyl Index for all encapsulant films, referred to the vibrations of the C=O functional group of ketons.

highest increase in crystallinity. However, under the conditions in which the aging tests have been carried out, the variations in crystallinity of all the samples are not very significant.

The obtained results from the UV aging tests show that a PV encapsulant degradation also depends on its formulation, that is, the kind and amount of the used additives, as well as from the used main polymer base. The presence of additives such as UV absorbers, antioxidants, UV stabilizers, plays an important role on the durability of the encapsulant and therefore on the reliability of a PV module. EVA-05HTL and POE-05HTL have a reduced amount of UV stabilizing additives

loaded in their formulation, which causes faster discoloration over time and compromises their long-term durability. The polymeric film that suffers the greatest loss of optical performance is POE-05HTL, which highly degrades already after the third UV aging, followed by EVA-3M and EVA-MW. In order to select an acceptable encapsulant, its loss in optical performance must not be higher than 2%. So, EVA-05 and POE-8110 maintain very well their optical properties even after accelerated UV aging. Probably, the improvement in the additives formulation determines the robustness of TPO-3M, which shows an increase in AT%.

Carbonyl Index reveals that all samples undergo chemical degradation due UV aging resulting in the formation of oxidation products. EVA-3M is the most chemically unstable encapsulant. All POEs undergo high chemical degradation, attributable to the additives loss and the consequent formation of oxidation products. Artificial UV aging causes no significant damage in EVA-MW, EVA-05, TPO and TPO-3M.

The obtained results highlight that the durability and UV resistance of encapsulant films can be significantly improved by adding in their formulation appropriate additives. Overall, the choice of a good PV encapsulant must be a compromise between good optical properties, thermal resistance at high temperature, transparency and photoaging resistance. Further studies are underway to evaluate the efficiency of mini-PV modules fabricated with the encapsulants investigated in this work, which revealed the best optical properties and the highest resistance to degradation caused by UV ageing.

Table 6

Summary of the encapsulants properties after UV aging.

Encapsulant	Thermal stability	Crystallinity %		T % at 550 nm		Additives loss	Yellowing AYI	Chemical degradation
		Unaged	$\Delta(\chi\%)$	Unaged	A(T %)			
EVA-MW	LOW	13.9	-0.82	92.47	-5.46	Negligible	1.01	Very low
EVA-OS	Low	13.2	0.33	88.24	0.26	Yes	1.55	Very low
EVA-05HTL	Low	12.9	0.94	89.62	-3.66	Yes	2.86	High
EVA-3M	Very low	14.3	-0.64	94.03	-6.62	No	0.74	Very High
POE-05	Very high	14.8	-1.93	92.68	-1.44	Negligible	2.01	High
POE-05HTL	Very high	10.8	-1.31	92.71	-15.30	High	3.63	High
POE8510	Low	8.2	-2.37	85.43	-2.45	Low	2.21	High
POE8110	Low	10.2	-0.55	90.50	0.80	High	2.18	High
TPO	High	14.6	2.1	89.64	-1.79	High	1.44	Low
MO-m	High	17.7	1.65	90.45	-2.95	Low	2.71	High
MO-3M	High	23.9	-1.01	86.78	3.16	No	2.03	Very low

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Valeria Fiandra: Writing — review & editing, Writing — original draft, Supervision, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Lucio Sannino:** Visualization, Validation, Software, Methodology. **Concetta Andreozzi:** Visualization, Software, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Giovanni Flaminio:** Software, Formal analysis. **Michele Pellegrino:** Formal analysis, Data curation.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

No data was used for the research described in the article.

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Supplementary materials

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